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QUANTUM CHEMICAL AND MOLECULAR DYNAMICS STUDY OF SPECIFIC COMPOUNDS DERIVED FROM WATERMELON RIND EXTRACTS AS AN ECO-FRIENDLY CORROSION INHIBITOR FOR ZINC SURFACES IN ACIDIC MEDIA

Aliyu, Musa^{1*}, Ibrahim, Imrana¹, Abdulsalam, Hamidat Ayomide², Shehu, Samira Adamu², Ibrahim, Ikilima Bandi²

¹Department of Pure and Environmental Chemistry, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, P.M.B. 2346, Sokoto State, Nigeria

²Centre for Advance Science Research and Analytical Services (CASRAS), Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, P.M.B. 2346, Sokoto State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author's Email Address; musa.aliyu1@udusok.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Quantum chemical calculations and molecular dynamics simulations were conducted on four compounds derived from watermelon rind ethanol extract: p-hydroxybenzoic acid (pHBA), pyridoxine (PDX), vanillic acid (VA), and sinapic acid (SA). Utilizing the density functional theory (DFT) module in Material Studio software (version 8.0), quantum chemical calculations was performed with the DND basis set and B3LYP functional. The analysis included various global descriptors to investigate the relationship between molecular structure and inhibition efficiency. Additionally, first and second-order condensed Fukui functions were examined to identify local reactivity parameters. Molecular dynamics simulations using Forcite quench revealed the mechanism of physical adsorption between individual molecules and the Zn (110) surface. The results provided valuable insights into the molecular interactions.

Keywords: Watermelon seed extract; Zinc metal; Corrosion Inhibition; Density functional theory; Molecular dynamic simulation

INTRODUCTION

Industrial processes such as pickling, cleaning, oil acidification, chemical and electrochemical etching, which involve acid solutions on metals, are unavoidable in various industries [1]. Zinc metal is widely used in construction due to its cost-effectiveness, excellent mechanical and electrical properties. However, like other metals, zinc's degradation when exposed to corrosive agents like acids poses significant challenges [2]. Implementing effective corrosion control measures can mitigate costs and ensure a safer working environment [3]. One approach is to use corrosion inhibitors, which can significantly reduce metal degradation. Nevertheless, many commercial inhibitors contain toxic compounds that raise environmental and health concerns [4]. As a result, research has shifted towards exploring and developing eco-friendly materials that can effectively inhibit metal corrosion in corrosive media [5]. Studies have shown that compounds extracted from plant materials exhibit promising corrosion inhibition properties, as reported by several authors [6, 7, 8].

The effectiveness of corrosion inhibitors depends on their molecular structure. Compounds that can donate electrons to unoccupied orbitals on the metal surface, forming coordinate covalent bonds, and also accept free electrons from the metal surface using their anti-bonding orbitals to form feedback bonds, are excellent corrosion inhibitors [7, 8].

Advances in computational modeling have enabled the exploration of complex systems at the molecular level. Molecular modeling software can provide valuable insights into molecular structure, electronic distribution density, and interaction energies, shedding light on the inhibition efficiency mechanism. Recent studies have utilized molecular modeling to investigate inhibition mechanisms on various scales [9]. This computational approach has been widely used to theoretically interpret experimental results, elucidate reaction mechanisms, and clarify chemical ambiguities. In this study, quantum chemical calculations and molecular dynamics simulations were employed to investigate the relationship between molecular structure and inhibition efficiency of four compounds present in watermelon rind ethanol extract (WRE): *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (*p*HBA), pyridoxine (PDX), vanillic acid (VA), and sinapic acid (SA) [10, 11].

Watermelon is a rich source of various bioactive compounds, including phenolic acids and other Phytochemical. Some literature sources confirmed the sources of these compounds interested in, specifically in watermelon. *p*-Hydroxybenzoic acid (*p*HBA) has been identified in watermelon rind extracts, contributing to their antioxidant and potential corrosion inhibition properties [10]. Watermelon is a good source of vitamin B6 [pyridoxine Pyridoxine (PDX)], which is essential for various bodily functions [11]. Vanillic Acid (VA) has been detected in watermelon rind extracts, exhibiting antioxidant and potential biological activities [10]. Sinapic acid (SA) has been identified in watermelon extracts, contributing to their antioxidant and potential health-promoting properties [10, 11].

These compounds (*p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, pyridoxine, vanillic acid, and sinapic acid) are good choices as ligands in computational corrosion inhibition studies due to presence of functional groups (e.g., -OH, -COOH) that can bond with metal surfaces, electron-rich molecules with aromatic rings and heteroatoms and potential for multiple bonding sites, enhancing adsorption and corrosion inhibition.

Zinc metal is chosen as a receptor in computational studies of corrosion inhibition due to industrial significance and corrosion susceptibility, well-characterized surface properties and relevance to real-world applications [2]. The Zn (110) surface is specifically chosen for its stability and high density, making it a suitable model for studying adsorption behaviour of corrosion inhibitors [17].

Therefore, this computational study aimed to determine the corrosion inhibition mechanism of these compounds on zinc (110) surface.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Density functional theory (DFT)

Quantum chemical calculations were performed on four compounds present in watermelon rind ethanol extract (WRE): *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (*p*HBA), pyridoxine (PDX), vanillic acid (VA), and sinapic acid (SA), as reported in previous studies [10, 11]. The goal was to evaluate the global and local reactivity active sites of these molecules. The density functional theory (DFT) electronic structure program DMol3 was used to perform simulations, employing restricted spin polarization with the DND basis set and B3LYP local correlation density functional [12].

Various quantum chemical descriptors were calculated, including E_{HOMO} , E_{LUMO} , absolute electronegativity (χ), global hardness (η), energy gap (ΔE_g), global softness (σ), ionization potential (I), electron affinity (A), global electrophilicity index (ω), energy of back donation (ΔE_{b-d}), and the fraction of electrons transferred (ΔN).

Electronegativity (χ) is defined as the negative of chemical potential, which is the first derivative of the total electronic energy (E) with respect to the number of electrons (N) at a constant external potential $v(r)$, as shown in equation (1).

$$\chi = -\mu = -\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N}\right) v(r) = \left(\frac{I+A}{2}\right) = \frac{-1}{2} (E_{HOMO} + E_{LUMO}) \quad \text{Eqn. (1)}$$

In equation (2), the global hardness η (eV) has been defined within DFT as the second derivative of E with respect to N at constant $v(r)$

$$\eta = \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2}\right) v(r) = \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N}\right) v(r) = \left(\frac{I-A}{2}\right) = \frac{-1}{2} (E_{HOMO} - E_{LUMO}) \quad \text{Eqn. (2)}$$

The mathematical expression of energy gap ΔE_g (eV) and global softness σ (eV)⁻¹ has been defined in equations (3) and (4) respectively.

$$\Delta E_g = E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO} \quad \text{Eqn. (3)}$$

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{1}{\eta}\right) \quad \text{Eqn. (4)}$$

In equations (5) and (6), the Ionization potential I (eV) and Electron affinity A (eV) are defined as the negative values of the energies of the highest occupied molecular orbital (E_{HOMO}) and of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (E_{LUMO}) respectively.

$$I: \text{Ionisation energy (eV)} = -E_{HOMO} \quad \text{Eqn. (5)}$$

$$A: \text{Electron affinity (eV)} = -E_{LUMO} \quad \text{Eqn. (6)}$$

These quantities above are related to the electronegativity (χ) and global hardness (η).

Global electrophilicity index ω (eV) and energy of back donation ΔE_{b-d} (eV) are defined in equation (7) and (8) respectively.

$$\omega: \text{Globalelectrophilicity index (eV)} = \frac{E_{HOMO} + E_{LUMO}}{8} \quad \text{Eqn. (7)}$$

$$\Delta E_{b-d}: \text{Backdonation (eV)} = \frac{E_{HOMO} - E_{LUMO}}{8} \quad \text{Eqn. (8)}$$

The fraction of electrons transferred (ΔN) from the inhibitor molecules to the zinc surface was calculated using equation (9).

$$\Delta N = \frac{(\chi_{Zn} - \chi_{inh})}{2(\eta_{Zn} - \eta_{inh})} \quad \text{Eqn. (9)}$$

Where χ_{Zn} and χ_{inh} are the absolute electronegativity of zinc metal and the inhibitor molecules respectively, and η_{Zn} and η_{inh} are the absolute hardness of zinc metal and the inhibitor molecules respectively.

The local reactivity of the studied compounds was analyzed using Fukui indices (FI) to identify regions susceptible to nucleophilic, electrophilic, and radical attacks. The Fukui function $f(r)$ is defined as the first derivative of the electronic density $\rho(r)$ with respect to the number of electrons at a constant external potential $v(r)$. Within the finite difference approximation scheme, we employed Mulliken population analysis to derive equations for electrophilic (equation 10), nucleophilic (equation 11), and radical (equation 12) attacks, depending on the direction of electron transfer. These equations were condensed to the nuclei using an atomic charge partitioning scheme, and all calculations were performed at the ground state geometry [13].

$$f_{Ak}^- = q_{Ak}(N_A) - q_{Ak}(N_A - 1) \quad \text{Eqn. (10)}$$

$$f_{Ak}^+ = q_{Ak}(N_A + 1) - q_{Ak}(N_A) \quad \text{Eqn. (11)}$$

$$f_{Ak}^0 = \frac{q_{Ak}(N_A + 1) - q_{Ak}(N_A - 1)}{2} \quad \text{Eqn. (12)}$$

The Mulliken charge on atom k is denoted by $q_{Ak}(N_A)$, which represents the electron density at a point r in space around the molecule with N_A total electrons. The anion and cation species are represented by $N_A + 1$ and $N_A - 1$, respectively, corresponding to the addition or removal of an electron from the LUMO or HOMO of the neutral molecule.

Molecular dynamic simulation (MDS)

Molecular dynamics simulations were performed using the Forcite quench module in BIOVIA Material Studio 8.0 to investigate the interaction between a single molecule of WRE compounds and the Zn(110) surface, aiming to determine the global energy minimum [16]. The simulations were carried out in an 8 x 7 super-cell using the COMPASS force field and the Smart algorithm. The Zn (110) surface was chosen for its high density and stability [17]. A Zn slab was built and cleaved along the (110) plane, ensuring it was larger than the inhibitor molecules to minimize edge effects during docking. The simulation parameters included a fixed temperature of 350 K, NVE ensemble, 1 fs time step, and 5 ps simulation time, with quenching every 250 steps. Surface atoms were constrained, and optimized structures of the inhibitor molecules were used. By simulating the adsorption of a single molecule of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (*p*HBA), pyridoxine (PDX), vanillic acid (VA), and sinapic acid (SA) onto the Zn (110)

surface, this is to gain insight into the interaction energies and their effect on inhibition efficiency. The interaction energy ($E_{\text{interaction}}$) and binding energy (E_{binding}) between each compound and the Zn (110) surface were calculated using equations (14) and (15), respectively [18].

$$E_{\text{interaction}} = E_{\text{system}} - (E_{\text{molecule}} + E_{\text{Zn}(110)}) \quad \text{Eqn. (14)}$$

$$E_{\text{binding}} = -E_{\text{interaction}} \quad \text{Eqn. (15)}$$

Where, E_{system} , E_{molecule} and $E_{\text{Zn}(110)}$ correspond to the total energies of the adsorbed Zn-molecule interaction in a gas phase, single molecule of the WRE inhibitor and the Zn (110) slab respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Density functional theory (DFT)

Table 1 presents the calculated molecular quantum chemical parameters, including E_{HOMO} , E_{LUMO} , absolute electronegativity (χ), global hardness (η), energy gap (ΔE_{g}), global softness (σ), ionization potential (I), electron affinity (A), global electrophilicity index (ω), energy of back donation ($\Delta E_{\text{b-d}}$), and the fraction of electrons transferred (ΔN). Figures 1-4 (a-d) illustrate the geometry-optimized structures, total electron density, highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO), and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) structures of the studied inhibitor compound

Table 1: Quantum chemical descriptors

Quantum chemical descriptors	pHBA	PDX	VA	SA
HOMO (orbital number)	36	45	44	59
LUMO (orbital number)	37	46	45	60
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-0.243298	-0.221886	-0.228143	-0.228959
E_{LUMO} (eV)	-0.044841	-0.022207	-0.044277	-0.071589
ΔE_{g} : Energy gap (eV)	0.198457	0.199679	0.183866	0.157370
Molecular mass (g/mol)	138.1220	169.1800	168.1400	224.2126
χ : Electronegativity (eV)	0.144070	0.122047	0.136210	0.150274
η : Global hardness (eV)	0.099229	0.099840	0.091933	0.078685
σ : Global softness (eV)	10.077750	10.016076	10.877487	12.708903
I: Ionization potential (eV)	0.243298	0.221886	0.228143	0.228959
A: Electron affinity (eV)	0.044841	0.022207	0.044277	0.071589
ΔN : Fraction of electrons transferred	0.313635	0.318302	0.314316	0.309692

According to previous studies [19], molecules with higher E_{HOMO} values tend to donate electrons more easily, while those with lower E_{LUMO} values are more likely to accept electrons. Among the WRE compounds, PDX has a high tendency to donate electrons due to its high E_{HOMO} value, whereas SA has a great potential to accept electrons due to its low E_{LUMO} value.

The energy gap (ΔE_{g}) provides further insight into the reactivity of the inhibitor compounds towards the zinc surface. A lower energy gap is associated with lower stability and a higher tendency to react [12]. The energy gap values for the extract compounds follow the order SA < VA < pHBA < PDX, indicating that SA has low stability and a high tendency to adsorb on the zinc surface.

Additionally, Sinapic acid (SA) having a lower ΔN (fraction of electrons transferred) despite a low ΔE_{g} (energy gap) could be due to steric hindrance. SA's molecular structure might lead to steric hindrance, reducing its ability to form strong bonds with the metal surface. Also, the orientation of SA on the metal surface might not be optimal for

electron transfer. Factors like π - π interactions, hydrogen bonding, or dipole-dipole interactions might influence SA's adsorption behaviour.

Mechanistically, a lower ΔN implies that SA might not be as effective at forming strong bonds with the metal surface, potentially reducing its corrosion inhibition efficiency compared to other compounds with higher ΔN values.

Global hardness (η) is a molecular property that influences reactivity and selectivity. Compounds with lower global hardness values tend to have better adsorption interactions with the zinc surface [20]. The global hardness values follow the order $SA < VA < pHBA < PDX$, suggesting that SA has a high tendency for well-established adsorption interactions with the zinc surface due to its low global hardness and high global softness.

Electronegativity (χ) is a key parameter that provides information about electron density within a molecule. The electronegativity trend observed is $SA > pHBA > VA > PDX$, indicating that PDX has the lowest electronegativity and a great tendency to adsorb on the zinc surface.

Figure 1: Structural properties of *p*HBA: (a) optimized structure (b) total electron density (c) HOMO orbital and (d) LUMO orbital

Figure 2: Structural properties of PDX: (a) optimized structure (b) total electron density (c) HOMO orbital and (d) LUMO orbital

Figure 3: Structural properties of VA: (a) optimized structure (b) total electron density (c) HOMO orbital and (d) LUMO orbital

Figure 4: Structural properties of SA: (a) optimized structure (b) total electron density (c) HOMO orbital and (d) LUMO orbital

Note: Atom legend: *white* H, *light gray* C, *red* O, *yellow* S and *blue* N. The iso-surfaces (larger lobes) depict the electron density difference; the *darker* regions show electron accumulation, whereas the *lighter* regions show electron

The fraction of electrons transferred (ΔN) follows the decreasing order PDX > VA > pHBA > SA, with PDX exhibiting the highest value. According to previous studies [22], when $\Delta N < 3.6$, inhibition efficiency increases with increasing electron-donating ability, whereas $\Delta N > 3.6$ indicates a decrease in inhibition efficiency with increasing electron-donating ability. Since all the studied compounds have ΔN values < 3.6, PDX is expected to have high inhibition efficiency due to its high electron-donating ability.

Also, the local reactivity of the compounds was analyzed using Fukui indices (FI). Table 2 presents the regions with the highest Mulliken and Hirshfeld charges for electrophilic (f^-) and nucleophilic (f^+) attacks in the studied compounds present in WRE.

Table 2: Highest values of Mulliken and Hirshfeld charges with respect to condensed fukui functions of the studied molecules

Molecules	Electrophilic attack (f^-)		Nucleophilic attack (f^+)	
	Mulliken	Hirshfeld	Mulliken	Hirshfeld
pHBA	O (10), 0.134	O (10), 0.133	O (8), 0.134	O (8), 0.133
PDX	O (12), 0.109	C (4), 0.118	N (3), 0.136	N (3), 0.130
VA	O (8), 0.119	O (8), 0.111	O (11), 0.141	O (11), 0.135
SA	O (10), 0.100	O (10), 0.101	O (15), 0.121	O (15), 0.115

The Fukui indices (f^-) measure a molecule's reactivity towards electrophilic attack, indicating its ability to release electrons, whereas Fukui indices (f^+) measure reactivity towards nucleophilic attack, indicating its ability to attract electrons [20, 23]. The analysis shows that pHBA has the highest Mulliken and Hirshfeld values for Fukui indices (f^-), suggesting its strong tendency to release electrons on the zinc metal surface during electrophilic attack.

Molecular Dynamic Simulation (MDS)

Figures 5 and 6 (a-d) show snapshots of the top and side views, respectively, of the lowest-energy molecular dynamics simulations for the interaction between a single molecule and the Zn(110) surface, performed using the Forcite quench module in Material Studio. The total energies were calculated by averaging the energies of the five most stable representative adsorption configurations.

Figure 5: Top view of the most stable configuration (a) Zn-*p*HBA system (b) Zn-PDX system (c) Zn-VA system and (d) Zn-SA system

Figure 6: Side view of the most stable configuration (a) Zn-*p*HBA system (b) Zn-PDX system (c) Zn-VA system and (d) Zn-SA system

The interaction energies ($E_{\text{interaction}}$) in Table 3 are all negative and of considerable magnitude, indicating stable adsorption structures. The more negative the interaction energy, the stronger the adsorption on the Zn metal surface. Previous studies have shown that more negative interaction energies correlate with better adsorption and higher inhibition efficiency [18,20]. Based on the adsorption energies in Table 3, the inhibition efficiencies of the inhibitors follow the trend: PDX > VA > SA > *p*HBA

Table 3: Energies descriptors for the lowest adsorption configuration for Zn-Inhibitor systems

Compounds	Interaction parameters (kcal/mol)				
	E_{system}	$E_{\text{interaction}}$	E_{molecule}	$E_{\text{Zn}(110)}$	E_{binding}
Phba	-49.2841	-20.4672	-28.8169	0.0000	20.4672
PDX	-11.6553	-23.0850	11.4297	0.0000	23.0850
VA	-35.0804	-22.5675	-12.5129	0.0000	22.5675
SA	-78.1700	-21.6814	-56.4887	0.0000	21.6814

CONCLUSION

The quantum chemical calculations and molecular dynamics simulations demonstrated the effectiveness of Watermelon Rind Extract (WRE) compounds in adsorbing onto the zinc metal surface. All tested compounds showed remarkable inhibition efficiency, highlighting their potential as effective corrosion inhibitors. This study suggests that WRE-derived compounds could be viable eco-friendly alternatives for corrosion protection in industrial applications, providing a barrier against corrosive agents and reducing corrosion-related damage.

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